

ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES: A CASE STUDY OF RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

The Nigeria University Commission (NUC) introduced the Entrepreneurship education into the curriculum of tertiary educational institutions to equip students and to make them self-relevance on graduation. As a means of controlling and reducing unemployment rate, self-employment was envisaged through the entrepreneurship education. It is on this realization that this study examined the entrepreneurship programmers in higher educational institutions in Nigeria and the extent of its implementation in Rivers State. To achieve this, survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 3554 lecturers in the nine higher institutions in the State. A multistage simple random sampling technique was used to sample 367 lecturers from the population. A self-constructed structured questionnaire of the Likert 4point rating scale of Very High Extent, High Extent, Low Extent and Very Low Extent, with ordinals values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts and a correlation coefficient of 0.81 was obtained to confer a higher reliability using Cornbrash Alpha. The researchers administered and retrieved, after filling the questionnaire copies by the help of paid research assistant s from the six sampled institutions. The data gathered were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, using Analysis Variance (ANOVA). It was found that majority of the entrepreneurship programmers were not available because of inadequate funding for the implementation of the programmed in higher institutions in Rivers State. However, the basic facilities/resources were found to be available for study. The study recommended that lecturers of the programmer should be more involved in practice than in theoretical work. School Management should formulate polices that will placed more emphasis on practical. The staff should be adequately trained and regularly retrained to meet the new demand for the programmers.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship programmed, extent of implementation, and higher institutions

Introduction

Entrepreneurship education has been defined in many ways by many authors and organizations. UNESCO (2012) stated that entrepreneurship education comprises all kinds of experiences that equip students with the ability and

Vision of how to access and transform opportunities. It includes creativity, innovation and risk taking as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve outcomes. Literature review show that the inclusion of Entrepreneurship Education into curriculum of tertiary education institutions stated in the United States of America as far back as 1947, unlike Nigeria case where it is a recent development that just begin in 2006 (Tahja, 2011). In view of the positive social and economic effects of Entrepreneurship Education, many education institutions, especially at the tertiary level, are now advancing in the implementation of entrepreneurial thinking and behavior to develop students' awareness of the relevance of Entrepreneurship training. Oviawe (2014) had reiterated the massive unemployment of graduates of Nigerian higher education institutions and had traced the problem to the disequilibrium between labour market requirements and lack of essential employable skills by the graduates. Finding from a three-week large scale, rapid national poll in 2004 jointly sponsored by National University Commission (NUC) and the Education Trust Fund (ETF) to determine the needs of the labour market which Nigerian university graduates are failing to meet are startling. The report revealed that of the 100 individuals and 20 organizations visited, 44% rated Nigeria science graduates as average in competence, 56% rated them as average in innovation, 50% as average rational judgement, 63% as average in leadership skills, while 44% as average in creativity. In the same report, 60% of the respondent rated the graduates as very poor in requisite skills such as literacy, oral communication, information technology, Entrepreneurial, analytical problem-solving, and decision making. Such findings explain why there has been very obvious increase in unemployment rate and the need for the introduction of Entrepreneurship education in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular (Oviawe, 2014). The above analysis necessitated the reason why in 2006, The Federal Government directed Nigeria Higher Education institutions (HEIs) to include entrepreneurship education (EEed) as a compulsory course for all students with effect from the 2017/2018 academic session which led to the mandatory inclusion of EEed in the curricula of all the tertiary education institutions in Nigeria (Aliu, 2008). The implementation of EEed in Nigeria and Rivers State is exemplified as most of the Universities in Nigeria now have a Centre for Entrepreneurship Education in their respective institutions. Entrepreneurship Education has continued to feature as a captivating theme in local summits and international conferences because of its potency as a tool for palliating unemployment and other socio-economic challenges hindering sustainable development, world over. It is a well-known fact that 12years after the introduction of EEed in in Nigeria tertiary institutions, many Nigerian graduates are still found looking for employment, it is also found that today many Nigerian graduates do not have access to EEed and training. Nwite (2016) reported that entrepreneurial learning environment and support tools were not

available in higher institutions in Nigeria and that adequate teachers to provide the needed appropriate skills and right attitude were not available and where they were available, they were in shortfall. The situation has been exacerbated by mass production of higher institutions graduates and school leavers from primary and secondary education institution without any commensurate arrangement for gainful employment or opportunities for self-reliance. This ugly posture has resulted in economic poverty among graduates, thus requiring an urgent action through the implementation of EEd in Nigerian higher institutions, especially in Rivers State. To corroborate the above (Okwelle and Deebom, 2016) stated that poverty and its symptoms were dominant features in Rivers State since the majority of the inhabitants, especially the youths were considered to be perpetually poor, unemployed and lacked marketable skills. Such funding explain why there has been very obvious increase in unemployment rate and the reason for integrating EEd into the tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Prior to this study, a pilot cross-sectional survey conducted by the researchers revealed that all the tertiary institutions in Rivers State have severally integrated the EEd programmer in their curricula. The previous observation shows a big mismatch between the integration of the EEd programmers in the higher institutions and the employment of the graduates of the higher institutions in the state. This phenomenon has called for a further scrutiny of the extent of implementation of the EEd programmers in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to provide empirical information on the extent of implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State. To achieve this purpose, the objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To evaluate different entrepreneurial activities available in higher institutions in Rivers State.
2. To evaluate the adequacy of funding resources available for the implementation of Entrepreneurship Studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.
3. To evaluate the competency of human resources available for the implementation of Entrepreneurship Studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.
4. To evaluate the adequacy of facilities/resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher education in Rivers State.
5. To identify the challenges facing the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What are the entrepreneurial programmers available in higher institutions in Rivers State?
2. To what extent is funding resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?
3. What is the competency of human resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?
4. To what extent are facilities resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?
5. What are the challenges facing the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean response of lecturers in Rivers State

University (RSU), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE), Kenule Beeson SaroWiwa Polytechnic (KenPoly) and Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic (ElechiPoly) on the availability of fund for implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean response of lecturers in University of Port Harcourt (UniPort), Federal College of Education (Technical) (FCE), KenPoly and ElechiPoly on the availability of human resources for implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean response of lecturers in RSU, IAUE, FCE, ElechiPoly on the availability of facilities resources for implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Methodology

The study adopted survey design; which enabled information collected from a large sample size. The population of the study consisted of 3554 lecturers in the nine higher institutions in Rivers State. A multistage simple random sampling technique was used to sample 367 lecturers from the population. Only those lecturer in the areas were entrepreneurship studies are taught were considered. The stages are Universities → Faculties → Departments. To collect information for the study, a self-constructed structured questionnaire of the Likert 4-point rating scale- of Very High Extent, High Extent, Low Extent and Very Low Extent, with ordinal numerical values of 4, 3, 2, and

1 respectively was used. The instrument was validated by three experts in the field. A correlation coefficient of 0.81 was calculated using Cronbach Alpha statistics to confer a high reliability on the instrument. The researchers administered the questionnaire copies with the help of paid research assistants from the six sampled institutions. The assistants also helped to retrieve the copies of the filled questionnaire. The data gathered were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the researcher questions. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, using analysis of variance (ANOVA). The data were presented with (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel software.

Result:

Research Question 1: What are the entrepreneurial programmers available in higher institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4.1: Frequency and Percentage Responses of Lecturers on Entrepreneurial Programmed Available in Higher Institutions in Rivers State

S/NO	Entrepreneurship Programmed			Available		Not Available		Total
				Freq	%	Freq	%	
A	Agricultural Programmed							
1	Snail Production	86	27	239	73	325		
2	Piggery	78	24	247	76	325		
3	Fishery	189	58	136	42	325		
4	Horticulture	101	31	224	69	325		
5	Animal Incarceration	61	19	264	81	325		
6	Veterinary Technology	90	28	235	72	325		
7	Gardening	134	41	191	59	325		
8	Livestock (Mammals)	171	53	154	47	325		
B	Production Skills/Trades			Freq	%	Freq	%	Total
9	Soap Making	64	20	261	80	325		
10	Toilet Roll Making	51	16	274	84	325		
11	Gold Smitten	88	27	237	73	325		
12	Furniture Making	173	53	152	47	325		
13	Tailoring	152	47	173	53	325		
14	Shoe Making	103	32	222	68	325		

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15	Bead Making	208	64	117	36	325						
16	Food/Catering Services	231	71	94	29	325						
17	Fashion Designing	183	56	142	44	325						
18	Textile Services	144	44	181	56	325						
C	Special Skills/Trades	Freq	%	Freq	%	Total						
19	ICT	216	66	109	34	325						
20	Laundry/Dry Cleaning Services			151	46	174	54	325				
21	Hair-Styling/Cosmetology			(Barbing,	325	Dressing)	200	62	125	38		
22	Photography	111	34	214	66	325						
23	Driving	89	27	236	73	325						
24	Music	193	59	132	41	325						
25	Instrumentation	55	17	270	83	325						
26	Arts/Printing and Graphics			110	34	215	66	325				

Source: Researcher's Field Result; 2018

In table 4.1 the programmers available are grouped under 'agricultural, production and special skills/trades with their respective subskills. Items with 50% and above were considered as entrepreneurial programmers that were available, while items that are less than 50% were considered not available.

Research Question 2: To what extent is funding resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4.2: Mean Responses of Lecturers on Availability of Funds for Entrepreneurial Studies in Higher Institutions in Rivers State.

SNO	Item	RSU	Uni Port	IAUE	FCET	Ken Poly	Elechi Poly	AVE	Rmk
27	Incentives are giving to lecturers	2.06	2.3	2.31	3.21	2.44	2.78	2.52	HE
28	Working tools are functional.	2.01	2.09	2.61	3.1	2.11	2.22	2.36	LE

Sustainability Journal

Research Article

29	Industrial machines are available	1.32	1.74	1.03	1.88	2.08	1.16	1.54	LE
30	Relevant texts and journals are stocked	2.41	2.04	2.83	2	2.61	3.01	2.48	LE
31	Workshop safety rules are strictly observed by trainees	3.67	3.91	4.01	3.77	3.81	3.9	3.85	VHE
32	Hand tools are available for students learning	3.82	2.55	2.78	1.71	1.84	2.03	2.46	LE
33	Workshop safety provision for lecturers and students	3.81	3.41	3.36	3.8	3.01	3.73	3.52	VHE
34	Maintenance of machines and equipment available	4.1	3.11	1.07	1.51	2.31	2.55	2.44	LE
35	Library facilities in the school	4.02	4.22	3.98	3.76	4.01	3.91	3.98	VHE
36	Working tools are available	2.81	2.51	2.49	2.71	2.03	2.08	2.44	LE
37	Industrial machines are functional	1.51	3.01	2.41	2.3	2.03	3.1	2.39	LE
38	Consumable materials are provided	2.67	3.05	2.98	2.63	3.51	3.71	3.09	HE
	Average	2.85	2.83	2.66	2.70	2.65	2.85	2.76	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result; 2018

The above table presents the decision rules as follows;

Very High Extent (VHE) $x \geq 3.49$; High Extent (HE) $x \geq 2.49 < 3.49$;

Low Extent (LE) $x \geq 1.49 < 2.49$; Very Low Extent (VLE) $x < 1.49$

Decision: since the Grand mean (2.76) is greater than the Criteria mean (2.50) the findings were therefore that there were high extent of availability of funds for the entrepreneurial studies.

Research Question 3: What is the competency of human resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurial studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4.3: Frequency and Percentage Response of Lecturers on Competency of Human Resources Available for Entrepreneurial Studies in Higher Institutions in Rivers State. S/No Variable Freq % Total

39 What is your highest qualification in Entrepreneurship:

Ph.D.	63	19.4	325	M.Sc.	182	56.0	325
B.sc /HND	80	24.6	325				
NCE/ND	0	0.0	325				
SSCE/NABTEB	0	0.0	325	FSLC	0	0.0	325

40 How long have you taught Entrepreneurship courses?

Less than 1 year	11	3.4	325				
1-3 years	13	4.0	325				
4-6 years	27	8.3	325				
7-9 years	214	65.8	325	10 years and above	52	16.0	325

41 What is your level of training acquired in Entrepreneurship?

Apprenticeship	0	0.0	325				
Technical college	0	0.0	325				
Industrial training	0	0.0	325				
Polytechnic	17	5.2	325				
Universities	303	93.2	325				

42 How long have you been professionally certified in Entrepreneurship?

Less than 1year	31	9.5	325				
1-3 years	79	24.3	325				
4-6 years	126	38.8	325				

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7-9 years 34 10.5 325

10 years and above 48 14.8 325

43 Lecturers' Years of Entrepreneurial Industrial Experiences

Less than 1 year 9 2.8 325

1-3 years 11 3.4 325

4-6 years 82 25.2 325 7-9 years 78 24.0 325

10 years and above 143 44.0 325

44 Lecturers' psychomotor skill for skilled based

Theory and practical 49 15.1 325

Theory only 174 53.5 325

Practical only 38 11.7 325

Skill acquisition 13 4.0 325

Vocational program 46 14.2 325

Source: Researcher's Field Result; 2018

Table 4.3 shows the distribution of the responses on the competency of human resources available for the entrepreneurial studies, with regards to lecturers' qualifications, length of teaching experiences, level of industrial training and psychomotor ability in practical demonstration skills.

Research Question 4: To what extent are facilities resources available for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4.4: Mean Responses of Lecturers on Facilities Resources Available for Entrepreneurial Studies in Higher Institutions in Rivers State

S/N	Item	RSU	Uni Port	IAUE	FCET	Ken Poly	Elechi Poly	AVE	Rmk
45	Adequacy of instructional resources	3.13	3.54	3.07	2.51	3.31	2.55	3.02	HE
46	Working tools are obsolete.	2.65	1.74	3.78	3.21	3.61	3.89	3.14	HE
47	Availability of industrial machines	1.61	2.12	2.05	3.08	1.52	3.09	2.24	LE

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48	Stocks of relevant texts and journals	3.65	3.09	2.99	2.05	3.62	2.78	3.03	HE
49	Well-equipped classroom	2.56	2.87	1.69	2.02	2.67	3.03	2.47	LE
50	Lack of resource center	3.04	3.98	3.32	3.77	3.21	3.98	3.55	VHE
51	Lack of workshop for technical base programmers	3.79	3.51	3.09	3.12	3.89	3.70	3.82	VHE
52	Maintenance of machines and equipment available	3.21	1.56	3.54	1.76	2.09	2.05	2.36	LE
53	Availability of library facilities in the school	2.67	3.82	3.9	4.27	3.61	3.12	3.56	VHE
54	Adequacy of water supply	3.45	3.9	3.12	3.04	3.00	3.93	3.40	VHE
55	Efficient supply of electricity	3.67	2.09	2.13	2.05	1.55	3.03	2.42	LE
	Average	3.04	2.93	2.97	2.81	2.92	3.20	2.97	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result; 2018

Table 4.4 shows that items 45, 46, 48, 50, 51, 53 and 54 have mean values higher than the criterion mean (2.50) and are considered high extent. All other items have mean values below criterion mean of 2.50 and are considered low extent.

Research Question 5

What are the challenges facing the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4.5: Mean Responses of Lecturers on Challenges Facing the Implementation of Entrepreneurial Studies in Higher Institutions in Rivers State

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S/NO	Item	RSU	Uni Port	IAUE	FCET	Ken Poly	Elechi Poly	AVE	Rmk
56	Lecturers'/Instructors' Capacity is Low	3.02	2.51	3.06	2.02	2.31	1.63	2.42	LE
57	Lack of infrastructural support	3.55	2.87	3.41	3.79	3.11	3.63	3.39	VHE
58	Absence of curricular capacity to support the training	1.53	3.8	2.42	2.87	1.52	2.1	2.37	LE
59	Lack of time from lecturers	2.78	2.06	2.67	3.09	2.01	2.11	2.45	LE
60	Excessive workload on the lecturers	2.04	1.78	3.42	2.08	1.93	2.32	2.26	LE
61	Improper timetable planning in the institutions	3.51	3.08	3.62	2.67	2.85	2.07	2.96	HE
62	The nature of the school environment	3.00	2.65	3.09	2.12	2.11	1.54	2.25	LE
63	Lack of favourable policy	3.90	3.42	3.07	3.55	3.21	2.99	3.35	VHE
64	Lack of government support	3.08	3.51	3.07	3.17	2.93	2.96	3.12	HE
65	Poor curriculum	2.08	3.08	1.76	2.94	1.99	2.70	2.42	LE
66	Over emphasis on theory delivery	3.08	3.75	3.42	2.80	3.08	3.12	3.20	HE
67	Absence of arch rese support and linkages	3.02	2.51	3.06	2.02	2.31	1.63	2.42	LE
68	Policies on statement are	4.55	2.87	3.41	3.79	3.11	3.63	3.56	VHE

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	entrepreneurship favourable									
69	Policies statement on entrepreneurship are not favourable	1.53	3.80	2.42	2.87	1.52	2.10	2.37	LE	
	Average	2.91	2.98	2.99	2.84	2.43	2.47	2.76	HE	

Source: Researcher's Field Result; 2018

Table 4.5 shows the mean responses of lecturers on challenges facing the implementation of entrepreneurial studies in higher institutions in Rivers State. Mean values higher than 3.49 but less than or equal to 4.00 was considered to be Very High Extent (VHE), mean values higher than 2.49 but less than or equal to 3.49 was considered to be High Extent (HE) while mean values higher than 1.49 but less than or equal to 2.49 was considered to be Low Extent (LE) and mean values less than 1.49 was considered to be Very Low Extent (VLE).

Hypotheses Testing:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean response of lecturers in RSU, IAUE, KenPoly and ElechiPoly on the availability of fund for implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4.6: Summary of ANOVA on Availability of Funds for Entrepreneurship Studies

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degree of Freedom (df)	Mean of Square (MS)	F-cal	F-crit	Remark
Between Groups	673	3	224.33	22.4	2.60	Rejected
Within Groups	3215	321	10.02			
Total						

Source: Researcher's Field Data; 2018 **Significant at .05, df = 3 and 321**

Table 4.6 shows F-distribution with F-calc of 22.4 is greater than the F –Crit of 2.60, therefore the Ho1 was rejected and Ha1 accepted. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of lecturers on the availability of funds for the entrepreneurship studies in the higher institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4.7: Schaffer's Post Hoc Multiple Comparison Test

Compared Groups	Paired Groups Values	F-crit	Absolute	F-	Remark
X ₁ – X ₃	RSU Vs IAUE			1.03	Not Significant
X ₁ – X ₅	RSU Vs KenPoly			1.45	Not Significant
X ₁ – X ₆	RSU Vs ElechiPoly		2.60	7.38	Significant
X ₃ – X ₅	IAUE Vs KenPoly			5.32	Significant
X ₃ – X ₆	IAUE Vs ElechiPoly			2.55	Not Significant
X ₅ – X ₆	KenPoly Vs ElechiPoly			3.04	Not Significant

Source: Researcher's Field Data; 2018

Table 4.7 shows that significant difference existed between entrepreneurship lecturers in RSU and ElechiPoly, IAUE and KenPoly as well as KenPoly and ElechiPoly respectively. X₁ – mean of group 1 (RSU); x₂ - mean of group 2 (UniPort), x₃ - mean of group 3 (IAUE), x₄ - mean of group 4 (FCET), x₅ – mean of group 5 (KenPoly), x₆ – mean of group 6 (ElechiPoly); x_G – Grand Mean

Result from Table 4.7 revealed that significant difference exist between entrepreneurship lecturers in RSU and ElechiPoly, IAUE and KenPoly as well as KenPoly and ElechiPoly respectively.

X₁ – Mean of group 1 (RSU)

X₂ – Mean of group 2 (UniPort)

X₃ – Mean of group 3 (IAUE)

X₄ – Mean of group 4 (FCET)

X₅ – Mean of group 5 (KenPoly)

X₆ – Mean of group 6 (ElechiPoly)

X_G – Grand Mean

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean response of lecturers in UniPort, FCE (T), KenPoly and ElechiPoly on the availability of human resources for implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4.8: Summary of ANOVA on Availability of Human Resources

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degree of Freedom (DF)	Mean of Square (MS)	F-cal	F-crit	Remark
Between Groups	183.5	3	61.16	8.42	2.60	Rejected
Within Groups	2330.75	321	7.26			
Total						

Source: Researcher's Field Data; 2018 Significant at .05, df = 3 and 321

Table 4.8 shows the F – distribution F – calc value of 8.42 and F – crit value of 2.60. Since the F – calc > F – crit, the Ho2 was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of lecturers on the availability of human resources for the implementation of the entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4.9: Scheffe's Post Hoc Multiple Comparison Test

Compared Groups	Paired Groups Values	F-crit	Absolute	F-	Remark
X ₂ – X ₄	UniPort Vs FCET			3.03	Significant
X ₂ – X ₅	UniPort Vs KenPoly			1.45	Not Significant
X ₂ – X ₆	UniPort Vs ElechiPoly	2.60		2.08	Not Significant
X ₄ – X ₅	FCET Vs KenPoly			1.84	Not Significant
X ₄ – X ₆	FCET Vs ElechiPoly			3.12	Significant
X ₅ – X ₆	KenPoly Vs ElechiPoly			2.01	Not Significant

Source: Researcher's Field Data; 2018

Table 4.9 shows that significant difference existed between the availability of entrepreneurship lecturers in UniPort and FCE (T) as well as FCE (T) and ElechiPoly respectively.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean response of lecturers in RSU, IAUE, FCE (T), ElechiPoly on the availability of facilities resources for implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4.10: Summary of ANOVA on Availability of Facilities Resources

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degree of Freedom (df)	Mean of Square (MS)	F-cal	F-crit	Remark
Between Groups	67.2	3	22.4			
Within Groups	3114.04	321	9.70	2.31	2.60	Accepted
Total						

Source: Researcher's Field Data; 2018 Significant at .05, df = 3 and 321

Table 4.10 shows F – distribution with F – calc value of 2.31 and F – crit value of 2.60. The H₀₃ was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of lecturers on the availability of facilities/resources for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

4.2 Summary of Major Findings:

The findings of the study are presented as follows:

1. That majority of the entrepreneurial education programmers were not available. This implies that entrepreneurship studies have not been implemented to a large extent in higher institutions in Rivers State.
2. The study found that funds are available for the implementation of entrepreneurial studies in Higher Institutions in Rivers State. This means that entrepreneurship education can be implemented in higher institutions in Rivers State to a high extent
3. The study also found that facilities resources are available for entrepreneurial studies in higher institutions in Rivers State and that the programmer can be implemented to a moderate extent.

4. The study found that the implementation of entrepreneurial studies in higher institutions in Rivers State is faced with challenges.

4.3 Discussion of Findings:

Table 4.1 shows the frequency and percentage response of lecturers on different types of skills available in different entrepreneurial programmers that are available in higher institutions in Nigeria. These skills includes agricultural skills (piggery, fishery, livestock), production skills (Bead Making, Fashion designing, food/catering services, tailoring, carving), marketing skills, managerial skills, accounting skills, special skills (hair dressing/cosmetology, barbing, ITC, photography, weaving, golds mitten, blacksmithing, welding etc). These findings are in line with that of Fawole (2006) as stated that vocational business can be viewed as that education which leads to the acquisition of practical and theoretical skills on various vocations such as carpentry, carving, drafting, sewing, tailoring, welding, blacksmithing, knitting, barbing, weaving, vulcanizing etc. The study also corroborates with Ofuasia, Nwalado and Dede's (2014) as stressed that students while in school will acquire necessary training and skills in accounting, management, entrepreneurship to identify an opportunity to exploit and eventual creation of their venture. As part of vocational education, it constitutes that part of education which prepares people for useful employment in reorganized occupations such as secretarial, accounting and administrative jobs and also be self-employed (Fawole, 2006). Baldwin (2002) argued that entrepreneurial skills students can acquire during training to enable them to be selfreliant include marketing skills, financial resources skills, self-motivation skills, time management skills, administrative skills, innovative skills, professional skills, practical skills etc, hence the need to incorporate and fully integrate entrepreneurial education in schools to ameliorate persistent socio-economic problems of graduates unemployment. The result of Table 4.2 shows the availability of funds for entrepreneurial studies in higher institutions in Rivers State. The findings of the study shows that incentives are giving to lecturers, relevant textbooks and journals are available, library facilities are also available, lack of training tools, lack of machines etc. The findings of this study is upheld by Offorma, Egbe and Eze (2012) as suggested that inadequate facilities and equipment for teaching and learning in practical-related courses were the reason why Entrepreneurship Education has not been able to record a significant impact in Nigeria industrialization drive and reduction of youth unemployment. Also, the result of this study agrees with Adiele (2010) and Maina (2014) that lack of support infrastructure and infrastructural failures results to high transaction costs which makes delivery very expensive and inefficient. The result of Table 4.3 shows that lecturers of entrepreneurship studies adopt theory only in teaching the course. The result also show that lecturers of

entrepreneurship programmers lack technical and industrial experience as bulky of them possesses qualifications from universities and polytechnics. These findings are in line with the study of Ogbiji, Ogbiji and Onigah (2017) who found that teachers teaching entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State consider themselves adequately qualified to teach the course but none of them has attended any special training in entrepreneurship training as course teachers. The findings of Table 4.4 revealed that entrepreneurship working tools are obsolete, availability of industrial machines and provision of well-equipped classroom are on low extent. These results corroborates with Ogbiji, Ogbiji and Onigah (2017) who found that course lecturers believe that there are no adequate logistics for teaching the course and that the course is theoretically taught without opportunity for learners to undertake practical as a result of lack of availability of machines and tools and that entrepreneurship programmers are and not well funded. Table 4.5 revealed that entrepreneurship training in higher institutions in Rivers State are not implemented as a result of challenges facing the programmers. From the findings of the study, the challenges include absence of research support and linkages, over emphasis on theory delivery, excessive workload on the lecturers, lack of infrastructural support etc. These findings are in agreement with Asiyai (2013) as found that entrepreneurial curriculum, lack of infrastructures and equipment's, lack of awareness among students and lack of skilled personnel are the major challenges facing effective implementation of entrepreneurship education in institutions of higher learning in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was deduced that entrepreneurship studies are implemented to a moderate extent in some trades while majority of the entrepreneurship trades are implemented to a low extent as a result of challenges facing the implementation of the programmers in higher institutions in Rivers State. The study also concluded that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers on the extent of implementation of entrepreneurship studies in higher institutions in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made;

1. Lecturers of entrepreneurship studies should be more involve in practical than theory based. This will enhance and make acquisition of skills more effective and easy.
2. School management should formulate policies that will favour the practice of entrepreneurship programmers in and outside the school.
3. Government should provide a well-equipped workshop for practicals.

4. Entrepreneurship programmer should be staffed with adequate and well-trained lecturers.
5. There should be adequate funding of the programmer by proprietors to ensure adequate logistics, provision of study materials.

Educational Implications

1. There is an implication that entrepreneurship programmed are not implemented to a high extent in higher institutions in Rivers State.
2. There is another implication that entrepreneurship programmed are faced with challenges.
3. Students of entrepreneurship studies have not embark on industrial tour and professionals from the industries are brought to teach those trades that are industrially affiliated.

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